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SICILIAN NATURALISTIC NEWS:

3 *Hermetia illucens*; 4 *Ancylolomia tripolitella*;
5 *Gavia immer*; 6 *Bucanetes githagineus*; 7 *Clubonia terrestris*.

How to contribute

Please download from the site www.ssn.it the form (word document) and compile it

Send it in .doc format to salvatore.surdo@unipa.it

Colour photos to enrich the observation reports are welcome. When sending a photo, be sure that you have rights to publish it. Photos will have a small format, so choose it considering that the subject must be clearly visible even in this case.

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3) *Hermetia illucens* (Linnaeus, 1758) (Diptera Stratiomyidae)

Source: 1) Forum Natura Mediterraneo (Romano M.) https://www.naturamediterraneo.com/forum/topic.asp?TOPIC_ID=33636

2) Forum Entomologi Italiani (Barraco L.) <http://www.entomologiitaliani.net/public/forum/phpBB3/viewtopic.php?f=401&t=11973&hilit=hermetia+illucens+sicilia>

3) Forum Entomologi Italiani (Altadonna G.)
<http://www.entomologiitaliani.net/public/forum/phpBB3/viewtopic.php?f=401&t=29291&hilit=hermetia+illucens+sicilia>

4-5) all the specimens housed in collection of G. Altadonna.

Category: Species of unusual occurrence for a given area

Number of individuals: 1 for each observation

Site location: 1) Palermo; 2) Marausa (TP); 3) Tremestieri (ME); 4) Vulcano Island (ME); 5) Lipari island (ME)

Date of observation: 1) 25.VIII.2007; 2) 13.VII.2010; 3-4-5) 2010 (without a specific date)

Records validated by: 1) Marcello Romano; 2) e 3) Marco Selis;

Reasons of interest: The species is not reported for Sicily (MASON, 2013). These are the first 5 records in Sicily before 2013; after 2015 the species was observed every year in Sicily with many records for year (see Facebook group: Fauna siciliana for details).

Reference.

MASON F., 2013. Updated Italian checklist of Soldier Flies (Diptera, Stratiomyidae). *ZooKeys*, 336: 61–78.

Marcello ROMANO, piazza A. Cataldo, 10 – 90040 Capaci (PA); Luigi BARRACO, via Passo Enea, 104 – 91100 Trapani; Giovanni ALTADONNA, C. da Filangeri s.n.c. 98125 Pistunina, Messina.

4) *Ancylolomia tripolitella* Rebel, 1909 (Lepidoptera Crambidae)

Source: author

Category: Species of unusual occurrence for a given area

Number of individuals: 2 (housed in collection of L. Morin)

Site location: Mazara del Vallo (Trapani)

Date of observation: 19.IX.2019

Notes of the observer: specimens sent to Lucio Morin for identification

Records validated by Lucio Morin

Reasons of interest: The species is not reported for Sicily. This is the first record.

Resource link:

<http://www.faunaeur.org>; <http://www.faunaitalia.it/checklist/>
Angelo DITTA, via Trieste n.16 – Mazara del Vallo (TP); Lucio MORIN, via Venezia, 10 – 34077 Ronchi dei Legionari (GO)

Ancylolema tripolitella Private collection L. Morin, 19.IX.2019 (leg. A. Ditta)

5) Common Loon *Gavia immer* (Brünnich, 1764) (Aves Gaviidae)

Source: author

Category: Species of unusual occurrence for a given area

Number of individuals: 1

Site location: Capo Santa Croce, Augusta (Siracusa)

Date of observation: 27.XII.2019

Notes of the observer: observed, for about a minute, one individual at 600 meters of distance from the coast.

Records validated by Salvatore Surdo

Reasons of interest: The species is not reported for Sicily (CORSO, 2005). This is the first record.

Reference.

CORSO A., 2005. Avifauna di Sicilia. *L'Epos ed.*, Palermo.

Manuel A. ZAFARANA, C.E.A. (Centro di Educazione Ambientale) Onlus, Niscemi, via A. Marsiano snc – 93015 Niscemi (CL, Italy).

6) Trumpeter Finch *Bucanetes githagineus* (Lichtenstein, 1823) (Aves Fringillidae)

Source: author

Category: Species of unusual occurrence for a given area and unusual number

Number of individuals: 1 - 6

Site location: Campobello di Mazara (Trapani)

Date of observation: several dates from 29.IX.2019 to 25.X.2019

Notes of the observer: all the observations were made inside and around a dump near Campobello di Mazara

Records validated by Salvatore Surdo

Reasons of interest: The species is observed almost every year in the circum-sicilian islands but it is rare in mainland. In most cases only one individual is observed.

Reference. CORSO A., 2005. Avifauna di Sicilia. *L'Epos ed.*, Palermo.

Antonino BARBERA, Via Giovanni Prati, 28 – 91022 Castelvetrano (TP).

Bucanetes githagineus, Campobello di Mazara 25.X.2019 (Ph. A. Barbera)

7) *Clubiona terrestris* Westring, 1851 (Araneae Clubionidae)

Source: authors

Category: Species of unusual occurrence for a given area

Number of individuals: 1

Site location: Saline di Trapani (TP)

Date of observation: 23.XI.2019

Notes of the observer: an adult male (housed in collection of A. Dentici)

Clubiona terrestris Saline di Trapani 23.XI.2019, leg. S. Surdo, Coll. A. Dentici.

Records validated by Antonino Dentici

Reasons of interest: The first record for Sicily (PANTINI & ISAIA, 2019).

Reference. Pantini P. & Isaia M., 2019. Araneae.it: the online Catalog of Italian spiders with addenda on other Arachnid Orders occurring in Italy (Arachnida: Araneae, Opiliones, Palpigradi, Pseudoscorpionida, Scorpiones, Solifugae). *Fragmenta Entomologica*, 51(2): 127-152. Online at www.araneae.it, accessed on 18.III.2020

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